

Persistent Identifiers: What They Are and Why You Should Care

[Researchers can spend as little as 17% of their time doing research](#) – it's no wonder so many are so frustrated. Persistent identifiers (PIDs), tools that support a connected and efficient research ecosystem, are part of the solution. PIDs can help you to stop wasting time and can reduce the administrative burden of research by identifying specific people, places, and outputs, connecting them together, and enabling that information to be passed back and forth automatically across different software systems.

A PID is both a unique label (a code or a number) for and a long-lasting link to a research 'entity' (i.e., a person, place, or thing). It's associated with additional information (known as 'metadata') about that person, place, or thing. For example, a PID for a journal article (a thing) would be associated with metadata such as the author's name (a person) and affiliation (an organization, aka a place). These, in turn, would be associated with their corresponding PIDs – in this case, the author's [ORCID](#) iD and the [Research Organization Registry \(ROR\)](#) ID for their institution, all of which can be linked.

Typically, a PID for a journal article would be a digital object identifier (DOI) and a PID for a person would be an ORCID iD – two of the best known and most used PIDs in the research world. In addition to publications, DOIs can also be assigned to many kinds of research outputs like datasets, videos, dissertations, and more. Researchers can then populate their ORCID records by linking to the DOIs for their outputs, either manually or by giving other organizations permission to do so. Researchers can even set this up automatically, for example, through [Crossref](#) and [DataCite](#)'s auto-update services.

PIDs provide a technical solution to costly and complex information challenges. Benefits of PID include:

- Reducing how many times the same information has to be rekeyed, through automation and pre-population of fields – saving time and minimizing errors
- Helping to answer important questions about return on investment and the long-term impact of research by enabling persistent links between researchers, their outputs, and their organizations
- Ensuring reliable citations in scientific literature, helping verify content/give credit where due
- Supporting open research and [FAIRness](#), outlined in the [Canadian Roadmap for Open Science](#)
- Enabling better strategic decision-making about national research priorities
- Reducing bureaucratic barriers to applying for grant funding
- Improving the understanding and practice of reproducibility and integrity of research

Thanks in large part to two national PID consortia – [ORCID-CA](#) (55 members) and the [DataCite Canada Consortium](#) (90 members) – Canada is seeing substantial growth in PID adoption. As of November 2025, there are roughly 175K active ORCID users in Canada and over 790K DOIs have been registered through DataCite Canada. A diverse group of Canadian research stakeholders (funders, institutions, libraries, publishers, researchers, and others) are now working together to build on this success. Facilitated by the [Canadian Persistent Identifier Advisory Committee](#) (CPIDAC), they are developing a national PID strategy to bring the benefits of PIDs to Canadian scholars – regardless of discipline, institution, language, or region.

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